

EOOSC Federation Technical Architecture: Evolution of Federating Capabilities and Federation Models

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Abstract

The EOOSC Federation is evolving towards a distributed ecosystem of autonomous EOOSC Nodes interconnected through common Federating Capabilities. While identity and catalogue federation provide essential foundations, additional architectural developments are required to fully support cross-node collaboration and access to distributed resources. This paper analyses the current EOOSC Federation architecture and identifies key evolution paths, including the introduction of additional Federating Capabilities, increased actionability, reduced dependencies on central components, and more distributed federation models. Building on the work of the EOOSC Beyond project, the paper outlines a vision for a more scalable, interoperable, and resilient EOOSC Federation.

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Executive Summary

The EOSC Federation is a federated ecosystem of autonomous EOSC Nodes collaborating through common policies, standards, and interoperable services. The EOSC Federation Handbook establishes the conceptual foundations of this vision, defining EOSC Nodes as autonomous entities capable of delivering services and resources while participating in federation-wide capabilities that enable interoperability and collaboration.

Significant progress has already been achieved through the implementation of the first Federating Capabilities, most notably the federation of identity and access management (AAI) and service catalogues. These capabilities provide the essential foundations for trust, resource discovery, and user access across the Federation. However, achieving the broader EOSC vision requires further architectural evolution. A federation based solely on identity federation and resource discovery cannot fully support the complex scientific workflows, operational processes, and cross-node collaborations expected by European research communities.

This paper analyses the current EOSC Federation architecture and identifies a set of evolutionary tracks that can strengthen its scalability, sustainability, and usability. First, the Federation should expand beyond the initial set of Federating Capabilities by introducing additional operational capabilities, such as service management, monitoring, accounting, and support services, together with specialised capabilities that facilitate access to and orchestration of distributed scientific resources. Second, Federating Capabilities should become increasingly actionable, enabling automated discovery, integration, and consumption through machine-readable interfaces and metadata. Third, the Federation should progressively reduce dependencies on central components where distributed alternatives can provide equivalent functionality while preserving federation-wide governance and interoperability. Finally, the Federation should evolve towards a multi-hub architecture where multiple EOSC Nodes can operate Federating Capabilities, improving resilience, scalability, and long-term sustainability.

The paper highlights concrete examples of these architectural evolutions, including federated catalogues, federated service management capabilities, and distributed orchestration services. It also discusses the role of supporting components such as the EOSC Node Registry, which can provide the discovery mechanisms necessary to enable actionable and distributed Federating Capabilities.

The work presented builds on the architectural activities carried out within the EOSC Beyond project and aims to contribute to the ongoing evolution of the EOSC Federation. Rather than proposing a radical redesign, the paper outlines a pragmatic evolution path that preserves the core principles of the EOSC Federation while enabling a richer, more scalable, and more operationally effective ecosystem. Ultimately, the EOSC Federation should evolve from a federation primarily focused on identity and resource discovery into a federation of interoperable operational and scientific capabilities capable of supporting seamless cross-border and cross-disciplinary research.

1. Introduction

The EOSC Federation is being established as a distributed ecosystem of autonomous EOSC Nodes collaborating through common policies, standards, and interoperable services. The EOSC Federation Handbook¹ and the EOSC Interoperability Framework² define the conceptual and technical foundations of this architecture, providing a common framework for the implementation of Federating Capabilities and the interoperability of participating Nodes.

The EOSC Beyond project plays a central role in this process. As one of the projects supporting the implementation of the EOSC Federation, EOSC Beyond is responsible for designing, prototyping, and validating key architectural building blocks required to operationalise the Federation. The project contributes directly to the development and validation of several Federating Capabilities, including service catalogue federation, identity federation, interoperability mechanisms, and the EOSC Node Registry. Through pilots and real-world implementations involving multiple EOSC Nodes, EOSC Beyond provides practical experience and evidence on how the Federation architecture can evolve to address emerging requirements.

Building on this work, this concept paper analyses the current status of the EOSC Federation technical architecture and proposes a coherent evolution strategy for the EOSC Federation, identifying a set of architectural evolution paths that could further strengthen the Federation. The objective is not to challenge the architectural principles established by the EOSC Federation Handbook, but rather to explore how these principles can be extended and refined as the Federation matures. In particular, the paper discusses the need for additional Federating Capabilities, increased actionability of federation services, reduced reliance on central components, and the emergence of more distributed and scalable architectural models capable of supporting the long-term objectives of EOSC.

EOSC Beyond provides practical experience and evidence on how the Federation architecture can evolve to address emerging requirements.

This document will support and enable community consultation on these topics. It will evolve in the coming months in response to feedback and will be extended to cover new areas.

¹ EOSC Federation Handbook: <https://zenodo.org/records/14999577>

² A landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework - Capabilities and Gaps: <https://zenodo.org/records/8399710>

2. EOSC Federation Architecture

2.1. Node Concept and Architecture considerations

The EOSC Federation Handbook defines the EOSC Federation as *a network of autonomous nodes – the EOSC Nodes – that interact with each other to deliver additional capabilities to users [...] to provide Europe's researchers with the necessary digital resources to conduct research within and across disciplines and borders according to the FAIR principles for data and open science, in a trustworthy and secure environment driven by the scientific communities.*

Within the EOSC Federation, Nodes represent national, regional, European or thematic research collaborations that provide services, datasets and other resources to their users. Each Node operates with its own governance models and maintains a well-defined portfolio of services and resources. Nodes are peers within the federation and collaboratively deliver added value to the users, forming a decentralised system of interconnected components. Each Node can interact directly with other Nodes, in compliance with standards, interfaces and policies defined by the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

From a conceptual perspective, this model resembles a distributed peer-to-peer (P2P) architecture, where Nodes act both as service providers and consumers without a central authority. While such an approach offers strong scalability and resilience, it also introduces significant technical and operational complexity, which has limited its adoption in large-scale federated research infrastructures.

Applying a full P2P model to the EOSC Federation would substantially increase the complexity of establishing and operating Nodes. In the current build-up phase, where many Nodes rely on in-kind contributions, such an approach would not be practical. These considerations have led to the adoption of a hybrid architectural model that balances flexibility with manageability.

In this hybrid model, presented in the Handbook, the EOSC Federation can be seen as a system of peer Nodes that retain autonomy over their governance, service offerings, and delivery channels. At the same time, Nodes collaborate through federating capabilities, some of which rely on shared or centrally operated components. These components are provided by Nodes acting in a **federator role** for specific capabilities and implementing a **hub-and-spoke model**, enabling coordination and interoperability across the federation while preserving the distributed nature of the system. This is represented in the overall architecture diagram of Figure 1. More details are available in chapter 4 of the Handbook.

Federating Capabilities are shared mechanisms that enable interoperability and collaboration between EOSC Nodes. They require the participation of multiple Nodes and provide federation-wide functionality that delivers value beyond the capabilities of any individual Node. Examples include federated identity and access management, resource

discovery, monitoring, service management, and distributed application deployment.

Services participating in a federating capability: services provided by a Node to connect to a Federating Capability enabled by another Node (e.g. for example a Node participating in the federated AAI by integrating its AAI proxy with the AAI Federation).

A **Federator** is a Node enabling a shared Federating Capability in the EOSC Federation for the benefit of other Nodes.

Figure 1. High-level architecture of the EOSC Federation (from EOSC Federation Handbook)

The Federation architecture defined in the Handbook provides a solid foundation for interoperability among autonomous Nodes.

The EOSC Federation is expected to begin its operation with an initial set of Federating Capabilities identified by previous EOSC-related projects as key to enable the sharing, discovery, access, and composition of services and research products that cater to the diverse needs of researchers and scientists. The mandatory capabilities, summarised in the table below, will be implemented by all EOSC Nodes and the EU Node.

Federating Capability	Description	Classification
AAI	Ensures the AAI interoperability across the EOSC Nodes by supporting federated authentication, Single Sign-On (SSO),	Mandatory ³

³ C.Kanellopoulos et. al., *EOSC AAI Architecture 2025 (March 2025)* <https://zenodo.org/records/15388270> (last accessed 17/12/2025).

Federating Capability	Description	Classification
	and secure token-based access to resources.	
Resource Catalogues and Registry services	Enables the discovery and access of resources provided through EOSC Nodes within the EOSC Federation.	Mandatory ⁴
Helpdesk	Integrates the helpdesks of EOSC Nodes within the EOSC Federation to provide a federated support channel between users and providers from nodes.	Recommended (Will become Mandatory in 2026)
Service Monitoring	Provide information about the quality and availability of services and resources made available through EOSC Nodes into the EOSC Federation.	Recommended (Will become Mandatory in 2026)
Service Management System	EOSC Federation FitSM-based Service Management System, defining the essential processes between EOSC Nodes to enable efficient IT service management within the EOSC Federation. It also includes Security Coordination between Nodes.	Recommended (Will become Mandatory in 2026)
Service Accounting	Provide information about the usage of services offered by EOSC Nodes within the EOSC Federation.	Recommended
Research Product Accounting	Provide information about the usage of research products made available through EOSC Nodes in the EOSC Federation.	Recommended
Order Management	Provides a framework that allows providers and users to manage the full lifecycle of service and resources requests and access granting across federated Nodes.	Recommended
Application Deployment Management	Automated deployment and execution of services across multiple federated nodes.	Recommended

Table 1. EOSC Federation: initial set of federating capabilities (from the EOSC Federation Handbook).

2.2. Implementation status of the EOSC Federation

The implementation of the EOSC Federation started in 2025, driven by the EOSC Federation build-up group, consisting of the Nodes of the first wave and the EU Node. During this initial phase, significant progress was achieved, including the establishment of the first-wave Nodes, many of which are expected to reach production readiness in 2026. Furthermore,

⁴ Manghi, P., Athanasiou, S., Karmas, T., & Szegedi, P. (2025), *Registration of EOSC Research Product Catalogues in the EOSC EU Node (3.1)*, <https://zenodo.org/records/17513272> (lastOSC-related accessed 8/6/2026).

Nodes are beginning to be connected to each other through the implementation of the first two federating capabilities, *Resource Catalogue and Registry services* and *AAI*.

The EOSC Federation is expected to enter its production phase in 2026. During the year, three additional Federating Capabilities, SMS, Helpdesk, and Monitoring, are expected to be designed, implemented, and adopted as mandatory capabilities for participating Nodes.

2.2.1. EU Node as a federator

Resource Catalogue and Registry services and AAI federating capabilities are currently enabled by the EU Node (federated AAI via GEANT MyAccessID) acting as the only federator in a hub-and-spoke model for both capabilities.

Figure 2. EOSC Federation Architecture with only the EU Node as a federator

2.2.2. Resource Catalogue and Registry services

The Resource Catalogue and Registry services federating capability is implemented through a central catalogue hosted by the EOSC EU Node, which aggregates resources and services metadata from all participating Nodes. The catalogue is accessible through the EOSC Resource Hub discovery portal⁵ (as well as open APIs), and supports discovery, access, and monitoring of EOSC services across the Federation.

The current implementation of this federating capability foresees that users go to the EOSC EU Node to discover EOSC Federation services and, then, be redirected to the Node(s) hosting the resources of interest.

This solution strictly depends on the EOSC EU Node: a user of a Node A must go to the EOSC EU Node to discover services and resources offered by other Nodes. Furthermore, it works well for scholarly communication aims, but it shows its limits when it is used by scientists to discover scientific assets. The adoption of a common metadata schema across several scientific disciplines causes the loss of fundamental information for the researchers.

⁵ Resource Hub: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/all>

Additional relevant use cases that are not supported are, for example, importing resources from one Node to another Node and pairing datasets and tools (see section 6.1).

2.2.3. AAI Federation

The Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) is a core federating capability of the EOSC Federation, enabling users to access services across EOSC Nodes in a seamless and secure way. In the EOSC model, services are onboarded to Nodes rather than directly to the Federation; therefore, AAI interoperability must be established at Node level so that access can be consistently extended across the wider federation. The EOSC AAI Architecture 2025⁶ describes the EOSC AAI Federation as the operational framework supporting federated authentication among EOSC Nodes, Single Sign-On (SSO) across Nodes and services, and token-based access to APIs and resources.

Current implementation

According to the EOSC AAI Architecture 2025, the current implementation of the EOSC AAI Federation follows a hub-and-spoke model. In this initial phase, EOSC Nodes connect through a central hub rather than establishing direct multilateral trust relationships with every other Node. The central hub provides the Trust and Identity Layers of the federation, while each participating Node is expected to operate at least one Infrastructure Proxy implementing the AARC Blueprint Architecture 2019⁷. Nodes may also operate one or more Community AAI for managing collaboration-specific identities, groups, and roles.

In practice, this model relies on MyAccessID as the common Identity Layer. Through this setup, users can authenticate using organisational identities, Community AAI, and other trusted sources, while Nodes use Infrastructure Proxies and token introspection to enable access across services and Nodes. This supports both browser-based Single Sign-On and cross-node API workflows using OAuth2 and OpenID Connect. This architecture was selected because it is implementable with current technologies and supports the immediate needs of the first wave of EOSC Nodes. At the same time, the EOSC AAI Architecture 2025 explicitly recognises this as an initial solution rather than the final target architecture of the AAI federation.

Target approach based on OpenID Federation

The target direction for the EOSC AAI Federation is a more distributed trust model based on the [OpenID Federation 1.0](#) standard (finalised in February 2026), moving beyond reliance on a central hub for trust brokering and enabling trust to be established directly between Nodes, while aligning with the evolution towards multi-hub federation models described in Section 7. While the EOSC AAI Architecture 2025 explicitly presents the current model as an initial implementation and identifies OpenID Federation as the direction for the longer-term evolution of the EOSC AAI Federation, the recent finalisation of the specification provides a solid foundation for this transition.

⁶ EOSC AAI Architecture 2025: <https://zenodo.org/records/15388270>

⁷ AARC Blueprint Architecture 2019: <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g045/>

2.2.4. Final considerations on the current status

While the current architecture provides a solid basis for interoperability among EOSC Nodes, the Federation remains in an early stage of maturity. Current implementations focus primarily on identity federation and resource discovery, while several operational and scientific use cases remain only partially supported. The next sections analyse the main architectural evolution tracks that could strengthen the EOSC Federation and enable more advanced cross-node interactions.

3. Evolutionary tracks of the EOSC Federation Architecture

Although the implementation of the EOSC Federation is progressing, several additional steps are needed to enable the EOSC Federation to fully fulfil its mission, making EOSC a web of FAIR data and related services enabling cross-Node use cases that make use of multiple services and datasets.

EOSC Beyond has identified four evolutionary tracks for the EOSC Federation architecture summarised in the table below and further detailed in the next sections.

Evolutionary Tracks	Description
More federating capabilities	<p>The two federating capabilities (AAI and Resource Catalogue and Registry services) currently enabled in the EOSC Federation are not sufficient to create an EOSC Federation able to serve its mission.</p> <p>They need to be complemented by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional Operational Federating Capabilities to set up a complete EOSC Federation operational layer • Generic and Thematic Federating Capabilities to facilitate access to and the exploitation of distributed EOSC services and resources.
Actionability of the federating capabilities	It should be possible to discover and programmatically access federating capabilities.
Reduce dependency on central components	A basic design principle of EOSC Federating Capabilities should be to minimise reliance on central components, enabling a gradual transition towards fully distributed Federating Capabilities where this is meaningful and manageable in terms of cost and operational complexity.
From one to more Federators - A distributed Hub-based architecture	<p>The hub-and-spoke model is sometimes the most practical and cost-effective solution to federated entities such as Nodes because it simplifies the work in large and complex systems.</p> <p>However, the current implementation of the EOSC Federation with a unique Hub (the EU Node) introduces dependencies and a potential single point of failure.</p> <p>The EOSC Federation should evolve towards a multiple-Hubs based architecture that improves federation fault-tolerance and scalability and enables decentralised management, flexibility and customisation.</p>

Table 2. Evolutionary tracks of the EOSC Federation Architecture

4. More Federating Capabilities for EOSC

Resource Catalogues and Registry services and AAI Federation federating capabilities deliver fundamental functions to implement the EOSC Federation. However, they are not sufficient to create the web of FAIR data and related services providing Europe's researchers with all the instruments to conduct research within and across disciplines and borders, in a trustworthy and secure environment driven by the scientific communities.

The EOSC Federation cannot be considered complete once AAI and Catalogue federation are available.

A mature EOSC Federation requires a broader ecosystem of operational and specialised Federating Capabilities that support both Federation operations and cross-node scientific workflows.

In line with what was reported in the EOSC Federation Handbook, these two federating capabilities need to be complemented by additional Operational Federating Capabilities, to set up a complete EOSC Federation operational layer (see Handbook section 4.3), and generic and thematic Federating Capabilities, to facilitate access to and the exploitation of distributed EOSC services and resources.

4.1. Operational Federating Capabilities

The establishment of the EOSC Federation requires the federation of operational and service management capabilities that enable Nodes to collaborate effectively in day-to-day operations. While the current EOSC Federation architecture already includes federated AAI and Resource Catalogues and Registry services capabilities, these alone are not sufficient to support the operational coordination required by a production-grade federation of autonomous Nodes.

In a federated environment such as EOSC, Nodes remain independent organisations with their own governance, operational models, and local infrastructures. However, users expect a coherent and reliable experience across the Federation. Achieving this objective requires the introduction of shared operational practices and interoperable management capabilities that allow Nodes to coordinate service delivery, incident management, monitoring, reporting, and support processes across organisational boundaries.

For this reason, the EOSC Federation Handbook introduced several operational Federating Capabilities, including Helpdesk, Monitoring, Accounting, and Service Management System (SMS) capabilities. These capabilities represent a fundamental evolution of EOSC from a metadata federation towards an operational federation.

A **federated Helpdesk** capability enables coordinated support across Nodes, allowing tickets, incidents, and service requests to be routed and managed transparently between organisations. This is essential to support cross-node use cases where users consume resources originating from multiple Nodes. Similarly, **federated Monitoring and Accounting**

capabilities provide federation-wide visibility on service health, availability, reliability, and resource usage, enabling operational oversight, SLA verification, capacity planning, and trust building across the Federation.

Among these capabilities, the **federated Service Management System (SMS)** plays a particularly strategic role. The SMS establishes a common operational framework based on shared processes, responsibilities, and management practices aligned with FitSM principles. Rather than replacing local SMS implementations, the federated SMS enables interoperability between the Service Management Systems operated by individual Nodes, defining how federation-level processes such as Incident Management, Change Management, Service Portfolio Management, Service Level Management, Continual Service Improvement, and Customer Relationship Management can be coordinated across organisational boundaries.

The federated SMS therefore becomes the operational backbone of the EOSC Federation, enabling Nodes to jointly deliver federated services while preserving their autonomy. It provides the governance and process framework necessary to manage dependencies, coordinate operational activities, and support the gradual evolution of EOSC towards a mature production federation.

Figure 3. EOSC SMS Federation–Node Integration Model.

4.2. Generic and Thematic Federating Capabilities

While the capabilities described in the previous section are essential to establish the Federation baseline, they are not sufficient on their own to support advanced scientific workflows requiring the seamless usage of distributed datasets, compute infrastructures, storage systems, and research platforms across multiple Nodes.

The implementation of Generic and Thematic Federating Capabilities should be considered a key priority for the evolution of the EOSC Federation.

One of the major challenges in EOSC is that scientific resources are inherently distributed across national, thematic, and institutional infrastructures, each operating with different technologies, policies, interfaces, and operational models. Researchers increasingly require integrated access to these distributed resources to execute complex workflows involving data discovery, data movement, distributed computing, AI training, large-scale analysis, and long-term data preservation. Supporting these use cases requires EOSC to progressively evolve beyond basic federation mechanisms towards generic and thematic federating capabilities specifically designed to facilitate resource interoperability and cross-node orchestration.

In this context, the EOSC Federation Handbook already introduces the concept of generic and thematic federating capabilities, including the **Application Deployment Management (ADM)** capability. ADM represents an important step towards enabling coordinated deployment and lifecycle management of applications across EOSC Nodes, supporting portability and interoperability of scientific applications within the Federation. However, the need for generic and thematic capabilities extends well beyond application deployment.

Future EOSC scenarios will require additional generic and thematic capabilities supporting areas such as distributed data access, federated compute orchestration, workload portability, cross-node storage integration, federated AI services, workflow execution, policy-aware scheduling, semantic interoperability, and distributed resource optimisation. These capabilities are necessary to reduce fragmentation and enable researchers to interact with the Federation as a coherent infrastructure rather than as a collection of isolated systems.

Generic and thematic federating capabilities can also significantly reduce the complexity for EOSC Nodes by abstracting technical heterogeneity behind common interfaces, APIs, and interoperability frameworks. Instead of requiring every pair of Nodes to establish ad hoc integrations, generic and thematic capabilities can provide reusable federation services that standardise interactions between infrastructures. This approach improves scalability, reduces operational overhead, and accelerates the onboarding of new Nodes and services into the Federation.

Moreover, generic and thematic federating capabilities are essential to support the evolution of EOSC towards machine-actionable and composable services. Scientific workflows increasingly rely on automation, orchestration, and dynamic resource allocation across distributed environments. Enabling these scenarios requires federating capabilities capable of supporting not only discovery but also execution, coordination, negotiation, monitoring, and optimisation of distributed resources and workflows.

The evolution and introduction of generic and thematic federating capabilities should therefore be considered a strategic priority for the long-term development of the EOSC Federation. While core federating capabilities establish the operational and governance

foundations of EOSC, generic and thematic capabilities will provide the technical mechanisms necessary to unlock integrated cross-node scientific services and enable EOSC to function as a truly federated digital research infrastructure.

5. Actionability of the federating capabilities

The EOSC Federation Interoperability Guidelines define Federating Capabilities as the mechanisms through which EOSC Nodes collaborate and exchange information to deliver Federation-wide services. They describe the policies, interfaces, information models, roles, and operational processes that enable interoperability among Nodes for capabilities such as Catalogue, AAI, Monitoring, Helpdesk, Service Management System (SMS), Accounting, and future Federation services. These specifications are a fundamental building block of the EOSC Federation architecture, providing a common framework that allows autonomous Nodes to operate as part of a coherent ecosystem.

As the Federation evolves, an important architectural objective should be to increase the **actionability of Federating Capabilities**. Today, many Federation interactions are still largely based on human-mediated processes, static documentation, manual configuration, and bilateral coordination among participating organisations. While this approach is adequate during the early stages of Federation deployment, it becomes increasingly difficult to sustain as the number of participating Nodes, services, users, and interactions grows.

A Federating Capability is actionable when it can be automatically discovered, understood, and consumed through standard interfaces without requiring manual configuration or bilateral agreements.

In a mature federation, Federating Capabilities should not only enable Nodes to exchange information, but also to automatically discover, access, and consume Federation services through standardised machine-to-machine interactions. In other words, Federating Capabilities should evolve from being primarily descriptive mechanisms towards becoming actionable Federation services. This evolution is also closely aligned with the FAIR principles, which emphasise machine-actionability as a prerequisite for scalable and automated interactions with digital resources. Just as datasets and services expose standardised interfaces for machine consumption, Federating Capabilities should enable Nodes and applications to seamlessly discover and interact with Federation services. Extending FAIR principles to Federating Capabilities can therefore facilitate the automation of cross-Node interactions and support the development of a more integrated and scalable EOSC Federation.

For example, a Node should not only be able to identify that another Node provides a Helpdesk, Monitoring, Accounting, or Catalogue capability. It should also be able to automatically discover the relevant endpoints, retrieve the required metadata, understand the supported interfaces, and establish interactions using standardised protocols. Similarly, operational tools should be capable of automatically exchanging monitoring information, routing support requests, synchronising catalogues, sharing accounting records, or orchestrating workflows across Nodes without requiring extensive manual intervention.

Improving the actionability of Federating Capabilities would provide several benefits for the EOSC Federation. These are summarised in the table below.

Benefits for the EOSC Federation	Details
Reduce operational complexity	Replacing manual procedures with automated interactions
Facilitate the onboarding of new Nodes	Reducing the amount of bespoke integration work required to join the Federation
Increase interoperability	Promoting consistent implementation patterns across different Nodes and technical environments
Create the foundations for more advanced Federation services	Including cross-Node service orchestration, distributed workload execution, automated policy enforcement, and dynamic resource allocation

Table 3. Actionability of Federating Capabilities - benefits for the EOSC Federation.

Achieving this vision requires Federating Capabilities to expose machine-readable information describing not only governance requirements and interoperability rules, but also the technical means through which interactions can be established. The Interoperability Guidelines should progressively evolve to define common APIs, endpoint descriptions, metadata schemas, service discovery mechanisms, and interaction patterns that can be consumed automatically by Federation services and operational tools.

The concept of actionability is therefore closely linked to service discovery. Before a Node can interact with another Node's Federating Capabilities, it must first be able to discover that the Node exists, determine which capabilities it supports, and retrieve the information necessary to establish interactions. This requirement naturally leads to the need for a Federation-wide mechanism capable of publishing and exposing machine-readable information about participating Nodes and their capabilities. Such a mechanism can provide the foundation upon which actionable Federating Capabilities can be built and represents a key enabler for the future evolution of the EOSC Federation architecture.

5.1. Enabling discoverability through a Node Registry

One possible implementation of this architectural requirement has been designed and prototyped within EOSC Beyond, an enhanced Node Registry that can act as such a Federation-wide mechanism.

The Node Registry was conceived to fill a critical architectural gap in the EOSC Federation: the lack of a dedicated mechanism to identify, search, and explore the participating Nodes and their capabilities. Its primary aim is to offer a reliable and scalable service for registering and managing metadata about EOSC Nodes, ensuring that each Node can be accurately described, discovered, and integrated into the wider Federation.

To achieve this, the Registry is designed to support both human and machine interaction. It enables the structured discovery of Nodes by providing access to information such as the

Node's legal entity, contact roles, services, and technical capabilities. While storing only a minimal set of descriptive metadata locally, the Registry provides the means to retrieve additional information on technical capabilities and service offerings from participating Nodes through standardised APIs. This enables seamless integration with other EOSC components. A key design goal is to ensure that every interaction with the Registry, whether registering a new Node or querying existing ones, is fully machine-actionable, making the service interoperable and future-proof.

Importantly, the Registry respects the autonomy of each Node. Every Node can independently expose its capabilities via its own dedicated endpoint, ensuring that metadata remains under the control of the Node itself. The system is also designed to be resilient and scalable, operating in a distributed manner that avoids centralised bottlenecks.

Figure 4. Discovering capabilities of a Node through the EOSC Node Registry

The Node Registry system is composed of two main components:

- 1. EOSC Node Registry (ENR)**: Acts as the central registration authority, holding descriptive metadata about each Node. It aggregates capability information collected from Node-specific endpoints and makes them accessible via a public REST API.
- 2. EOSC Node Endpoint (ENE)**: A service that resides on each EOSC Node, exposing real-time metadata about that Node's capabilities. This includes supported federated services like AAI, Resource Catalogues, Monitoring, and more.

6. Reduce dependency on central components

The current EOSC Federation architecture represents an important step towards the establishment of a pan-European ecosystem of interoperable research infrastructures and services. The architecture defined in the EOSC Federation Handbook successfully balances the autonomy of participating EOSC Nodes with the need to provide common Federating Capabilities that enable collaboration across the Federation. However, as the number of participating Nodes, services, users, and scientific domains continues to grow, it becomes increasingly important to assess the long-term sustainability of architectural patterns that rely heavily on central components.

Dependencies on central components can introduce several challenges. From a technical perspective, **central services may become operational bottlenecks** as Federation adoption increases. Their scalability requirements, operational complexity, and maintenance costs tend to grow proportionally with the size of the Federation. Furthermore, **central components may become single points of failure**, affecting the availability of Federation-wide capabilities in the event of technical incidents, cyber-security events, funding disruptions, or organisational changes.

Beyond technical considerations, excessive **centralisation may also create governance and sustainability concerns**. EOSC is fundamentally conceived as a federation of autonomous organisations, infrastructures, and communities that collaborate through common policies and interoperability mechanisms. Strong dependencies on central services can inadvertently concentrate operational responsibilities and decision-making authority, potentially limiting the flexibility of participating Nodes to adopt solutions that best fit their national, thematic, or organisational requirements. Such dependencies may also increase the perceived barriers for new organisations wishing to establish and operate EOSC Nodes.

Central components should be minimised when distributed alternatives can provide equivalent functionality while preserving interoperability and governance.

Reducing dependencies on central components does not imply eliminating Federation-level coordination or abandoning common interoperability frameworks. On the contrary, Federation-wide policies, standards, interfaces, and governance mechanisms remain fundamental to ensure trust and interoperability across EOSC. The objective is rather to progressively decentralise the delivery of Federating Capabilities, moving from architectures where capabilities are delivered through a small number of central services towards architectures where responsibilities can be distributed across multiple interoperable providers, hubs, or Nodes. In such a model, EOSC Nodes retain their autonomy while continuing to benefit from common Federation capabilities delivered in a more resilient, scalable, and sustainable manner. While the delivery of Federating Capabilities is decentralised across multiple Nodes and Federators, their implementation should remain compliant with the EOSC Interoperability Framework, common information models, and Federation governance processes. Mechanisms for certification, validation, and compliance assessment will therefore remain essential to ensure interoperability and maintain trust across the EOSC Federation.

This architectural evolution is particularly relevant for operational Federating Capabilities, where several existing implementations still rely on central services. Exploring **more distributed approaches can increase Federation resilience, facilitate onboarding of new Nodes, foster innovation, and better align the operational implementation of EOSC with its underlying vision as a federation of collaborating peers**. The following sections analyse this evolution through concrete examples, focusing on catalogue federation, helpdesk and application deployment management federating capabilities.

Challenges	Description
Central components may become operational bottlenecks	Scalability requirements, operational complexity, and maintenance costs of central components tend to grow proportionally with the size of the Federation.
Central components may become single points of failure	The availability of Federation-wide capabilities can be affected in the event of technical incidents, cyber-security events, funding disruptions, or organisational changes.
Governance and sustainability concerns	Dependencies on central services can concentrate operational responsibilities and decision-making authority, potentially limiting the flexibility of participating Nodes to adopt customised solutions.

Table 4. Challenges introduced by central components.

6.1. Federated Catalogues

The evolution of the Resource Catalogues and Registry services Federating Capability towards a more distributed setup is key for the establishment of a more powerful EOSC Federation. Current catalogue federation mechanisms mainly support metadata discovery and publication workflows. A distributed catalogue architecture can extend this role by enabling the discovery of machine-readable information about resources, services, and Federating Capabilities maintained by participating Nodes, while reducing dependencies on central components. This discovery layer can provide the foundation for more advanced federation capabilities, including service composition, workflow portability, and cross-node orchestration (for example, ADM Federating Capability, see section 6.3). Together, these developments can support the transition of EOSC to evolve from a federation primarily focused on resource discovery towards an ecosystem capable of supporting integrated cross-node scientific workflows and advanced federated services.

EOSC Beyond has designed and prototyped an evolution of the Resource Catalogues and Registry services Federating Capability that overcomes the current implementation based on a central catalogue. This enhanced version foresees that users can discover EOSC resources from their node of reference. It enables these two main user scenarios:

- As a user of Node A, I am able to discover resources of Node B and combine them with resources of Node A.
- As Node Operator of Node A, I want to list in Node A resources from Node B.

Both cases require appropriate mechanisms to authorise discoverability of resources between Nodes.

The EOSC Beyond implementation of the Resource Catalogues and Registry services Federating Capability is based on an interoperability layer enabling cross-node resource discovery within the EOSC ecosystem: the resource catalogue *federation proxy*. The federation proxy provides a common search and discovery interface enabling interoperable queries across Resource Catalogues, ensuring protocol-level compatibility and allowing existing clients to consume federated results without modification.

Each Node exposes this capability through its Node Registry Client, advertising support for cross-node listing and search. Crucially, the architecture preserves the principle that **each node's Resource Catalogue remains the single point of truth for all resources onboarded in that node**; the federation layer never duplicates or overrides local catalogues but instead queries them dynamically at request time. When a federated query is executed, the proxy orchestrates parallel calls to the Resource Catalogue endpoints of participating nodes, normalises the returned metadata, and aggregates the results into a unified response. This aggregated view forms the basis of a **virtual catalogue**, a logical collection that presents distributed resource repositories as a single, coherent catalogue without centralising or replicating data. The virtual catalogue can be consumed by other EOSC Core Components (Front Office, Monitoring, etc) installed in federated Nodes, where each resource can explicitly indicate the node from which it originates. Architecturally, the federation proxy abstracts node-to-node communication, capability discovery, and response harmonisation, while maintaining strict separation between local truth sources and federated views. By aligning with the Resource Catalogue's API model and preserving node autonomy, the solution enables scalable, transparent, and interoperable federated search across Resource Registries in the entire federation.

An additional advantage of the Virtual Catalogue approach is the possibility to create multiple catalogue views tailored to the needs of specific user communities, domains, projects, or policy objectives. Rather than maintaining a single Federation-wide catalogue, Virtual Catalogues can dynamically query resources from multiple Nodes according to predefined criteria, creating specialised discovery environments without duplicating information. For example, a Virtual Catalogue could provide a consolidated view of all resources relevant to molecular biology research, independently of the Nodes where those resources are hosted. Similarly, Virtual Catalogues could be established for specific scientific domains, research infrastructures, countries, funding programmes, or thematic initiatives. This approach enables the EOSC Federation to offer community-oriented discovery services while preserving Node autonomy and maintaining each participating catalogue as the authoritative source of information.

A potential challenge of the Virtual Catalogue approach is the increased latency associated with querying multiple distributed Resource Catalogues. However, this can be mitigated through well-established distributed-system techniques. Virtual Catalogues may cache frequently accessed metadata, execute queries in parallel across multiple Nodes, and maintain limited replicas of commonly used information while preserving each Node's catalogue as the authoritative source. In addition, resilience mechanisms such as graceful

degradation and the use of cached information can minimise the impact of temporary Node unavailability. As a result, a distributed catalogue federation can preserve the benefits of local ownership and autonomy while delivering the performance and reliability expected by EOSC users.

Figure 5. EOSC Federated Search information flow.

6.2. Helpdesk

The evolution of the Helpdesk federating capability represents a critical shift from a centralised support mechanism toward a fully distributed architecture. To minimise central operational dependencies while ensuring a seamless, coordinated support channel between users and providers, a phased implementation strategy has been designed. This transition allows the federation to scale incrementally, moving from basic email-mediated routing to an automated, multi-node synchronised ticketing ecosystem.

Phase 1: FSU Mailing List (E-mail Option A)

In the initial deployment phase, the focus is on establishing baseline connectivity with minimal technical overhead.

- **Operational Setup:** At this stage, the Federated Support Unit (FSU) functions strictly as a shared mailing list rather than an integrated ticketing platform. All participating node helpdesks are linked to the FSU primarily through standard email integration.
- **Support Workflow:** End-users continue to contact individual EOSC Nodes directly for localised issues. Cross-node or federation-level issues are handled manually by a rotating duty crew assigned to manage the FSU mailing list. This approach provides a low barrier to entry but relies heavily on human-mediated coordination.

Figure 6. The Three-Phase Evolutionary Roadmap of the Helpdesk federating capability towards a fully distributed architecture

Phase 2: Email Integration (E-mail Option B)

As the federation matures, interaction patterns transition from a purely centralised mailing list toward targeted, node-to-node operational links.

- Operational Setup:** Nodes begin establishing direct email-based integrations with one another, driven by concrete, cross-node scientific use cases. For instance, nodes frequently collaborating on shared datasets or compute workflows build localised tracking links (e.g., integrations between Nodes N2, N3, and N5).
- Support Workflow:** The rotating duty crew continues to manage the core FSU channels, while the remaining nodes progressively join the interconnected framework. This phase reduces the single-point-of-dependency on a central list manager by distributing ticket context directly between interacting peers.

Phase 3: Full Sync + Entry Point (Full API-Based Integration Option C)

The final target state achieves decentralised operations through complete API-based synchronisation, transforming the capability into an actionable federation service.

- Operational Setup:** All EOSC Nodes are connected via an established, reliable integration layer driven by a dedicated transport AMS (Argo Messaging System). Rather than hosting a monolithic ticket repository, the FSU queue is synced across every Node's helpdesk, so any FSU ticket is visible to all duty agents regardless of which Node they work at.
- Support Workflow:** A central hub helpdesk remains visible to the public to serve as a unified entry point and execute automated triage algorithms. However, once a ticket is auto-triaged, it is dispatched via the transport layer directly to the relevant nodes. Support agents and specialised duty crews operate entirely within their own native,

local helpdesk environments. This eliminates the need to log into a central platform, fully preserving node autonomy while guaranteeing federation-wide operational resilience.

6.3. Application Deployment Management (ADM)

The Application Deployment Management (ADM) Federating Capability is particularly relevant in this context, as it was designed from the outset as a distributed capability. Rather than relying on a central service, it enables EOSC Nodes to expose and consume resources through common interfaces, supporting cross-Node orchestration and demonstrating how future Federating Capabilities can natively embrace the distributed nature of the EOSC Federation.

According to the EOSC Federation Handbook, the federation of the Application Deployment Management (ADM) will allow EOSC users to easily deploy and/or execute applications seamlessly across one or more Nodes. Researchers are able to discover application recipes and perform their deployment and execution on EOSC Nodes that have the appropriate computing resources. These recipes (or blueprints) are typically defined using a standardised language such as OASIS TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications). A TOSCA template defines the application architecture (e.g. two computing nodes with access to a network with outbound connectivity) and references automated installation procedures of the software via DevOps-like approaches (e.g. an Ansible role to install the application and the required dependencies via the corresponding software package repositories).

Figure 7 provides a diagram of the ADM federating capability. Nodes that participate in the EOSC federation may offer this capability by exposing a service that implements the ADM standardised API, as defined in the ADM Interoperability Guideline⁸. This API allows users to inspect the available resource allocations on an EOSC Node and list the application recipes supported to be deployed. EOSC Beyond has produced a machine-readable specification of the ADM API⁹.

Each Node can offer the ADM capability using their preferred technology stack, considering their technical expertise, underlying computing infrastructure and security and local administrative procedures.

In the context of EOSC-Beyond, a reference implementation of the ADM API is provided via ADIM (Application Deployment Management based on the Infrastructure Manager)¹⁰, which results in the evolution of the EOSC Deployment Service, based on the Infrastructure Manager (IM)¹¹, towards a federated EOSC environment. However, a set of automated

⁸ Application Deployment Manager Interoperability Guideline.

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20596323>

⁹ EOSC Application Deployment Manager API.

<https://github.com/EGI-Federation/eosc-application-deployment-manager>

¹⁰ ADIM. Application Deployment management with the Infrastructure Manager.

<https://github.com/grycap/adim>

¹¹ Infrastructure Manager. <https://www.grycap.upv.es/im>

compliance tests is provided¹² so that other services that implement the ADM API can be automatically tested to comply with the API spec (and in turn comply with the ADM Interoperability Guideline).

Figure 7. An overview of the Application Deployment Management federating capability.

Figure 8 shows the delivery of the ADM capability to users of a particular Node. Users can obtain the list of applications supported and deploy them in the Node’s cloud infrastructure (e.g. an Infrastructure as a Service OpenStack-based Cloud). A Node may decide to allow its users to deploy applications via its ADM service on other external Clouds (e.g. a public Cloud hyperscaler such as Amazon Web Services or a European Cloud provider such as Open Telekom Cloud).

Figure 8. A Node offering the ADM capability (optionally with access to external Clouds)

Figure 9 shows the federating capabilities of ADM. In a), a user from a Node is using the ADM capability to deploy an application on another Node’s Cloud infrastructure. This typically requires using a compatible AAI approach. In b), a service running on Node B that

¹² <https://github.com/grycap/adm-compliance-tests>

requires data-processing capabilities is using Node A's ADM capability to perform application deployment on Node A's Cloud infrastructure.

Figure 9 ADM accessing other Node's Cloud infrastructure (a), and services from other Nodes using the ADM capability to deploy applications (b).

7. From one to more Federators - A distributed Hub-based architecture

The current EOSC Federation architecture described in the EOSC Federation Handbook follows a hybrid federated approach in which EOSC Nodes maintain their autonomy while relying on a set of Federating Capabilities enabling interoperability and collaboration across the Federation. In this context, the adoption of a **multi-hub architecture** represents a natural evolution path to support the scalability, sustainability, resilience, and inclusiveness objectives of the EOSC Federation.

Figure 10. Evolution of the EOSC Federation Architecture from a centralised to a distributed Hub-based architecture and, potentially, to a mesh-based model¹³.

A fully centralised federation model, where a single central entity delivers all common federation services and coordination functions, may initially simplify onboarding and operational management. However, such an approach introduces structural limitations that become increasingly problematic as the Federation grows in scale, diversity, and complexity. Centralised architectures tend to create operational bottlenecks, governance concentration, limited flexibility for domain-specific requirements, and potential single points of failure. They also risk reducing the autonomy of participating Nodes, which is a foundational principle of the EOSC Federation model.

In contrast, a multi-hub architecture distributes federating responsibilities across multiple interoperable hubs operated by different organisations or communities. Each hub can provide one or more Federating Capabilities, such as Helpdesk, Monitoring, Service Management System (SMS), Accounting, Workflow Orchestration, or Data Transfer, while remaining compliant with common EOSC interoperability guidelines and policies. EOSC Nodes can then interact with a hub according to their operational needs, scientific domains, maturity level, and governance preferences.

The adoption of a multi-hub architecture represents a natural evolution path to support the scalability, sustainability, resilience, and inclusiveness objectives of the EOSC Federation.

¹³ From Peter Sezgedi DG CNECT C.1, "EOSC-01-01 Projects and the EOSC EU Node / Federation presentation", May 2026

This approach offers several strategic and technical advantages summarised in table 5 and detailed below.

Benefits	Description
Scalability	Operational load and service delivery responsibilities can be distributed across multiple hubs. New hubs can be added without redesigning the entire federation.
Resilience and operational continuity	Failures in one hub are isolated and do not affect others.
Preserving the autonomy and diversity of EOSC Nodes	Each hub can deliver its own set of Nodes, enabling tailored governance.
Flexibility and customisation	Each hub can be adapted to the needs of a specific technical/thematic domain or to a geographical area.
Innovation and technological evolution	Hubs can experiment with alternative implementations, specialised capabilities, and emerging technologies while remaining interoperable with the rest of the Federation

Table 5. Benefits of a multi-hub architecture.

First, a multi-hub architecture significantly improves **scalability**. As the number of EOSC Nodes, services, datasets, and users increases, operational load and service delivery responsibilities can be distributed across multiple hubs rather than concentrated within a single central infrastructure. This enables incremental federation growth without requiring continuous vertical scaling of central services. New hubs can progressively emerge to support specific geographical areas, scientific domains, operational communities, or technical specialisations.

Second, the model enhances **resilience and operational continuity**. The distribution of federation services across multiple hubs reduces dependency on single operators and mitigates risks associated with outages, governance changes, funding discontinuities, or operational failures. Federation capabilities can be replicated or jointly delivered by multiple hubs, improving redundancy and service availability across the EOSC Federation.

Third, a multi-hub architecture better **preserves the autonomy and diversity of EOSC Nodes**. Different communities and national infrastructures often operate under different governance frameworks, legal environments, operational procedures, funding models, and technology stacks. A distributed hub model allows these differences to coexist while still enabling interoperability through agreed interfaces, APIs, metadata models, and federation protocols. This is particularly important in the EOSC context, where participation is based on collaboration among autonomous organisations rather than hierarchical control.

Another important advantage concerns **innovation and technological evolution**. A centralised architecture tends to slow down innovation because architectural changes and service evolution must be coordinated centrally and deployed uniformly across the

Federation. In a multi-hub architecture, hubs can experiment with alternative implementations, specialised capabilities, and emerging technologies while remaining interoperable with the rest of the Federation. Successful approaches can progressively evolve into Federation-wide practices. This model creates a more flexible and innovation-friendly ecosystem aligned with the experimental and evolving nature of EOSC.

The multi-hub model is also particularly relevant for the delivery of specialised federating capabilities supporting advanced scientific use cases. Capabilities such as distributed data processing, workflow orchestration, federated AI services, data analysis platforms, trusted research environments, and domain-specific access mechanisms often require expertise and operational models that are difficult to centralise efficiently. Multi-hub architectures enable these specialised capabilities to emerge close to the communities that develop and operate them while still making them interoperable at Federation level.

Finally, the adoption of a multi-hub architecture aligns well with the long-term vision of EOSC as a system of interoperable and collaborative infrastructures rather than a monolithic platform. It allows the Federation to evolve incrementally from the current operational setup towards a more distributed and mature federation model without imposing disruptive architectural transitions. In this sense, the multi-hub approach represents a pragmatic compromise between the operational simplicity required during the early phases of Federation deployment and the scalability and decentralisation objectives required for the long-term evolution of EOSC.

Looking beyond the initial multi-hub architecture, the EOSC Federation could further evolve towards a **mesh-based model** in which EOSC Nodes are connected to multiple Federators simultaneously, each providing different Federating Capabilities or serving different communities and use cases. For example, a Node could consume identity federation services from one Federator, catalogue federation services from another, and specialised capabilities such as workload orchestration, data management, or operational support from additional Federators. In such a model, Nodes would no longer rely on a single federation hub but would dynamically interact with multiple hubs according to their needs and capabilities. This evolution would further increase the resilience, flexibility, and scalability of the EOSC Federation, while preserving Node autonomy and enabling the emergence of specialised centres of expertise. The EOSC Federation would thus progressively evolve from a federation supported by a limited number of shared hubs towards a true federation mesh, where interoperable Federating Capabilities can be provided, discovered, and consumed across a distributed network of collaborating Nodes.

8. Conclusions

The EOSC Federation has successfully moved from a conceptual vision towards an operational reality. The establishment of EOSC Nodes, the publication of the Federation Handbook and Interoperability Guidelines, and the implementation of the first Federating Capabilities represent major milestones in the development of a European-wide federation of research services and resources.

At the same time, the current architecture should be regarded as the beginning of the Federation journey rather than its final destination. While federated identity management and resource discovery provide essential foundations, they alone cannot support the full range of operational and scientific interactions required by the European research community. The long-term success of the EOSC Federation will depend on its ability to offer a richer ecosystem of interoperable capabilities that simplify access to distributed resources, support cross-node collaboration, and enable increasingly automated and integrated research workflows.

This paper has identified four complementary architectural evolution paths. The Federation should expand the portfolio of available Federating Capabilities, increase their actionability through machine-readable interfaces and automated discovery mechanisms, progressively reduce dependencies on central components where appropriate, and move towards a more distributed multi-hub architecture capable of improving resilience, scalability, and sustainability. These evolutions are not independent; together they form a coherent roadmap towards a more mature federation model.

The architectural work carried out within EOSC Beyond demonstrates that many of these evolutions are already technically feasible. The challenge for the coming years is therefore not only technological but also organisational, requiring coordinated efforts across EOSC Nodes, projects, and governance bodies. By embracing these evolutionary paths, the EOSC Federation can strengthen its role as the digital backbone of European Open Science and provide researchers with seamless access to services, data, and computing resources across disciplines, institutions, and national borders.